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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-IV. Preparation of 2-Aryl-5-(2',4'-bis-*p*-chlorophenyl-amino-*s*-triazin-6'-ylaminomethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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1,3,4-Oxadiazoles are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of physiological properties like anti-tubercular¹, bactericidal^{2,3}, fungicidal⁴, analgesic, antipyretic^{5,6}, hypoglycemic⁷, hypnotic and sedative⁸. *s*-Triazine derivatives have also been reported to possess antiviral⁹, antimalarial^{10,11} and anticancer^{12,13} properties. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to synthesise new derivatives and to screen them for their antimicrobial activity.

Keeping this in view, some new 2,5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles having *s*-triazine moiety have been prepared by the condensation of different aromatic acids with the hydrazide of 2,4-bis-*p*-chlorophenyl-amino-6-carbethoxymethylamino-*s*-triazine in presence of POCl₃ to obtain the 1,3,4-oxadiazoles of type 1.

1; R = Aryl

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes using a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu-IR-435 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) were recorded on a Varian FT-80A spectrophotometer with tetramethylsilane as the internal reference.

2,4-Bis(p-chlorophenylamino)-s-triazin-6-ylamino-acylhydrazide: A mixture of 2,4-bis-*p*-chlorophenyl-amino-6-carbethoxymethylamino-*s*-triazine¹⁴ (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in dioxane was refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (85%), m.p. 243° (Found: C, 48.53; H, 3.79; N, 26.35. C₁₇H₁₆ON₈Cl₂ calcd. for: C, 48.8; H, 3.83; N, 26.79%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (NH), 3 350-3 280 (doublet, NH), 1 660 (C=O), 820 (C₃N₃) and 800 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl).

2-Phenyl-5-(2',4'-bis-*p*-chlorophenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-ylaminomethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole: A mixture of 2,4-bis(*p*-chlorophenylamino)-*s*-triazin-6'-ylamino-acylhydrazide (0.01 mol) and benzoic acid (0.01 mol) in POCl₃ (5 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (69%), m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 56.93; H, 3.49; N, 22.11. C₃₄H₁₈ON₈Cl₂ calcd. for: C, 57.14; H, 3.57; N, 22.22%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 (NH), 1 570 (C=N), 1 090 (C-O-C), 820 (C₃N₃) and 760 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); τ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 1.9-2.8 (12 H, m, Ar-H), 6.7 (s, NH) and 7.2 (2H, s, CH₂).

Similarly, other substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles of the type 1 were prepared by condensation of different aromatic acids with 2,4-bis(*p*-chlorophenylamino)-*s*-triazin-6-ylaminoacylhydrazide. The physical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-5-(2',4'-BIS-*p*-CHLOROPHENYLAMINO-*s*-TRIAZIN-6'-YLAMINO-METHYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE*

R	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p. °C
Phenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ ON ₈ Cl ₂	75	> 300
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₃	71	> 300
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₃	79	260
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₃	60	255
<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	63	190
<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	68	212
<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	71	176
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	60	219
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	62	215
Cinnamyl	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	76	166
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	59	168d
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₉ Cl ₂	62	220d
<i>o</i> -Acetoxyphenyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₈ Cl ₂	74	90
2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	78	171
2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₈ Cl ₂	60	217
Benzyl	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	70	222
3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	75	228d
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₂ Br	76	226
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ ON ₈ Cl ₂	80	> 300
3-Pyridyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ ON ₈ Cl ₂	69	800d
4-Pyridyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ ON ₈ Cl ₂	74	161d
3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₈ Cl ₂	67	218

*Satisfactory analyses were obtained.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial assay was carried out with the compounds (Table 1) using cup-plate¹⁵ method against species of gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, *S. albus*, gram-negative bacteria like *Escherichia coli* and fungi like *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 50 μg when zone of inhibition from 9 to 38 mm were observed depend-

ing on different compounds. Maximum zone of inhibition was observed in compound having R=*p*-hydroxyphenyl against *S. citreus* (23 mm), R=*m*-hydroxyphenyl against *S. aureus* (38 mm), R=4-pyridyl against *S. albus* (26 mm), R=phenyl against *E. coli* (27 mm). It was however observed that the fungi *A. niger* and *P. chrysogenum* were moderately sensitive to the compounds under investigation.

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Synthesis of some Indole Derivatives

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INDOLE derivatives have marked hypotensive¹, anthelmintic², antibacterial³ and antiparkinsonian⁴ activities. 1,3- and 1,4-dizaepinoindoles are potent tranquilisers, sedative and antidepressants⁵⁻⁹. The substitution at 3-position in indole nucleus markedly affects hypotensive activity. Here, we report the

synthesis of some new 1,2,3-trisubstituted-indole derivatives.

The starting compound used for the synthesis of desired indole derivatives was *N*-cyanoethyl aromatic amine (2) which on condensation with α -benzoyl ethyl bromide followed by cyclodehydration in the presence of P_2O_5 in xylene gave *N*-cyanoethyl-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (3). The disappearance of quartet due to methine protons at δ 5.2 and appearance of $C_{\alpha}-CH_3$ protons at δ 2.5 indicated the cyclisation. The reduction of 3 either with $LiAlH_4$ in THF or Raney nickel in hydrazine gave *N*-propylamino-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (4). The appearance of doublet in the ir spectra at $3\ 300\ cm^{-1}$ indicated the reduction of $C\equiv N$ group to CH_2NH_2 group. The compound 4 further reacted with various compounds having different structural moieties (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the melting points reported are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Hitachi spectrophotometer, ir spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. All the compounds were satisfactorily analysed for C, H and N. Physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

4-Methyl-N-cyanoethyl-p-toluidine (2): A mixture of *p*-toluidine (53.5 g, 0.5 mol) and acrylonitrile (26.5 g, 0.5 mol) and cupric acetate monohydrate (2.5 g) was heated under reflux for 0.5 h at 100 and 140° for 3 h. The dark reaction mixture was distilled under reduced pressure to remove the unreacted *p*-toluidine. On cooling, the separated solid on recrystallisation from ethanol gave 2 (40 g, 53%), m.p. 102° (Found: C, 82.15; H, 8.13; N, 9.50. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2$ requires: C, 82.19; H, 8.21; N, 9.58%); λ_{max} (ethanol) 265 and 300 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 200–3 300 (NH), 2 250 ($C\equiv N$), 1 700 ($C=O$) and 1 600 cm^{-1} ($C=C$); δ (TFA) 2.1 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.8 (2H, t, CH_2CN), 3.7 (2H, t, NCH_2) and 7.1 (5H, s, Ar H); $m/z M^+$ 160.